

APlus
PREMIUM PRODUCTS

The Stasher

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Showtime

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Origin of the Sphinx

April 3, 1990

Sphinx

Head - 6m tall

25:1

My Head .24 tall

12.97
8.33
4.64

33
15.5
7
108.5
11
15.5
9
46.5

33
15.5
10.1800
930
700
620
80

130
.64
1520
780
83.20

4.64
3.84
8.48
#24
22
15.5
4
620

Sphinx Terraces and 'Amphitheater'

The area around the Sphinx is characterized by four principal levels or terraces cut into the limestone bedrock at the ^{lower} east-southeast of the Mokattam Formation at Giza just before it dips into the sand of the lower desert. Terrace I, at elevation 7.98 (17.31 M.S.L.) supports the two large temples - the Sphinx Temple and the Khafre Valley Temple - in front of the Sphinx. Terrace 2 is bounded on the north by a ledge about 4.25 m high. It is bounded on the west by ~~the~~ ^{western} walls of the Sphinx Temple which ~~are~~ on this side are ^{partially} cut out of the natural rock for a ~~de~~ height of 2.62 m. In the corridor between the Sphinx Temple and Valley Temple the terrace is bounded by a ledge, 1.55 m high, that is transected by the narrow channel ~~which~~ or socket for the ^{missing} granite sheathing of the Valley Temple's North wall, west end. ~~The west wall of the Valley Temple bounds the Terrace I~~ Behind the West wall of the Valley Temple Terrace I ~~is terminated~~ terminates at a low ledge that slopes from north near the causeway walls, ~~to the south~~ ^{to} ~~at~~ ^{more} than 83 m to the south gradually decreasing in height.

The bedrock surface has never been cleared ^{southwards} beyond the large limestone block wall and mudbrick walls attached to the south side of the Valley Temple, so the limit of Terrace 2 in that direction is unknown. The area immediately to the front of the Valley Temple is ~~covered~~ ^{and cannot} covered by a limestone pavement and stage ~~at~~ built right up to the ~~front of the~~ granite casing of the temple facade. This was made in 1969 for performances connected with the Cairo Millennium celebration. To either side of the modern platform, the two ^{stone} entrance

a corridor which formed with the Sphinx Temple North wall at the N end of this corridor there is a step up 2.90 m to the level of Terrace II.

18.93
8.38
1.55

$$\begin{array}{r} 7.112 \\ 7.42 \\ \hline .70 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 12 \\ 64 \\ \hline 48 \\ 72 \\ \hline 7.68 \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{r} 3.5 \\ .64 \\ \hline .60 \\ 90 \\ \hline 9.60 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 64 \\ 4 \\ \hline 256 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} .64 \\ 22 \\ \hline 128 \\ 128 \\ \hline 14.08 \end{array}$$

ramps leading toward the Valley Temple doors remain exposed. These and the terrace immediately before the temple facade were ^{cleared and} mapped by Holscher in 1912. The stone ramps cross a narrow channel ^{.70 deep} formed ~~into~~ in the rock ~~to~~ to meet the terrace before the temple where it ~~was~~ is 7.68 wide. The part now covered has cuttings that Holscher found for placements for pairs of ~~Sphinxes~~ Sphinxes at each Valley Temple entrance and for a shrine that stood ^{before} the center of the temple facade. The floor of Terrace I at the east end of the corridor between the Sphinx Temple and Valley Temple is composed of enormous blocks of limestone that have been laid into, and made flush with, the surrounding bedrock. The channel running N-S before the Valley Temple phrases out here to merge with the general level of the rock floor ~~thru~~ far out in front of the Sphinx Temple. Holscher did not clear the area of the Sphinx Temple at all, and Baraiee only cleared ~~out~~ to the east of the ~~Sphinx~~ Sphinx Temple for about 6 or 7 m. ~~He~~ ^{He} built a retaining wall to hold back the unexcavated debris from the front of the temple. This was taken down by Hassen who began to move the massive accumulation of sand here, but he only cleared the bedrock surface for 9 or 10 m east of the Sphinx Temple. ^{In 1981-2} I cleared ~~the~~ the sand which had drifted over the area ~~etc~~ Hassen cleared ~~at the~~ east of the corridor between the two temples. I traced a 2.56 m thick badly graded mudbrick wall attached to the end of the north Valley Temple entrance ramp. ~~The wall ran~~ for a distance of 14 m to the north. It is clear from what has been exposed of Terrace I in front of the Sphinx Temple that ~~its~~ ^{the} surface is sloping gradually to the east. This was also indicated by

8.48
8.24
216.72
8.36

150
80
000
1200
12,000

100
100
000
1000
10,000

in June 1980

The excavation of Zahi Hawass / about 30 m east of the Sphinx Temple on its axis. Two probe trenches within a 10x10 m excavation exposed the finished - fairly smooth, bedrock floor under about ~~5~~ m of sand at elevations _____ and _____.

Terrace 2 thus extends at least this far ^{in front} ~~east~~ of the Sphinx Temple at a gradual ~~at~~ slope to the east.

It probably extends another 10 or 15 m further, considering the fact that the ^{North} ledge bounding the terrace runs 45 m east of the Sphinx Temple before it disappears under the sand and ~~and~~ modern road.

An outer limit ^{for the terrace} of 50 m east of the temple ~~for~~ is indicated by a core drilling ^{done} ~~20 m east~~ of Hawass's excavation done by the Institute for Underground Water of the Eg. Min. of Irrigation in Sept-Oct 1980. This was located about on line of the S.T. axis and 20 m east of Hawass's excavation. The drill went through 16 m of sand and debris in ground water after _____ m, before hitting a hard ^{stone} surface. The core sampler pulled up red granite fragments from this surface. ~~It is~~ ~~hard to conceive~~ Since ^{the} granite had to have been imported from outside Giza, this may be granite that dropped to the bottom of a harbor facing the Sphinx Temple and Valley Temple. It is hard to conceive of a granite monument in situ on a lower terrace. The drilling indicates that Terrace 1 ends somewhere in the 20 m between Hawass's 1980 excavation and the drilling, ~~as~~ as a drop-off that could be the ancient quay. This is probably about 45 m east of the Sphinx Temple, given the termination of the N Ledge. (see above). Terrace 2 was no mean engineering feat - just on its own, measuring more ~~than~~ 70 m ~~and~~ east-west by more than 150 north-south, on an area of 12,000 m². The

New Figure

is roughly paralleled by that of the "Amphitheater" N cliff and the modern road ^{to the Khufu Pyr.} along ~~the~~ the face of the cliff. Managieles already suggested that the embankment on which the road is founded may have been that of an ancient supply ramp for building the pyramids — ~~perhaps that it could have been used for pyramid building, stone taken for the Sphinx area.~~ This is implicit in Reischer's suggestion that the Sphinx is in the "old Cheops quarry." There are reasons to believe the main quarry for the Khufu pyramid was directly to the south of ~~the~~ that pyramid. The suggested supply route could equally have served the Khafu Pyramid. In any case, the general excavation into the rock layers in the Sphinx area had sider ~~oriented~~ oriented — the orientation of the Khufu causeway. However, ~~the end result of~~ the ~~temple~~ terraces, temples — and Sphinx statue complex that they sculpted into the rock is oriented quite accurately east-west (Petrie). As the removed surface to achieve the terracing, and the core for the Sphinx lion body, the builders brought the alignment closer to the cardinal directions in a series of successive approximations until — greater leveling allowing greater precision of alignment. This kind of "honing in" on ~~the~~ the ~~medi~~ meridian is also exhibited ~~at~~ the ~~base~~ base of the Khufu and Khafu pyramids.

AT END OF TERRACES DISCUSSION

The ~~terraces~~ ~~exposed~~ ~~place~~ when the surface of Terrace I are exposed east of the Sphinx Temple indicate that it was carefully graded to slope down from the front of the temple. The same ~~same~~ Similarly ~~is true of~~ the corridor between the temples, the corridor north of the S.T. and the area south of the

check spot height of drawing

$$\begin{array}{r} 3^4 \\ 18 \\ -64 \\ \hline 172 \\ 108 \\ \hline 11.52 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 1 \\ .64 \\ 4 \\ \hline 256 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 2 \\ .64 \\ 5 \\ \hline 320 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} .64 \\ 12 \\ \hline 128 \\ 64 \\ \hline 7.68 \end{array}$$

V.T. all slope subtly to the east. The strip of Terrace I behind the V.T. slopes from the end of the Khafre causeway, where a granite lined drain runs under the south wall of the causeway, to the south of the temple. All these slopes were designed to carry rain water away from the temples.

(The builder achieved a similar, ~~but much greater~~ effect on a much greater scale at the Khafre pyramid, where the rock surface was cut to a uniform slope away from the court and enclosure wall around on all 4 sides ~~of~~ of the pyramid).

Immediately at the base of the Sphinx T. NE corner, there is a square patch of rock left unfinished from the floor grading and leveling. It measures ~~3.20~~ 3.20 m square and ~~has~~ exhibits the "removal channels" left created to "waste" the rock surface. Just beside this patch, to the NE, there is a rectangular trench, 2.56 (N-S) x 11.52 (E-W) cut into Terrace I along the N-Ledge. The trench was probably done for the cutting of an unfinished jamb here that penetrates the rock ledge for 7.68 m. The entrance has the characteristic drum roll over the doorway, it is very rough and unincised.

Most of Terrace I was taken over by the ^{bedrock} floor area of the two O.K. temples. ~~That~~ That of the Sphinx T. was cut into the terrace to a depth of about 30 to 60 cm. The ^{original} bedrock floor of the V.T. ~~is mostly~~ is covered by ^{original} a ^{original} masonry of modern ^{cement} in fill. However it is probably ~~at least~~ close to the elevation of the ST, ca. 8.00, since, ~~at~~ the pavement is around 8.60

Check elevations in 2 chambers & at site's southeast

1978 SPHINX CLEARING NOTES

S - Channel about 50-60 cm deep (Meeting of Members I and II in floor)

Firm bedrock slopes into depression

Feb. 18 Keystone Shaft

The outline of the Sphinx...
indications of where...
The north side of the...
the west of the North Lodge...
as a part of the Sphinx...
The ledge...
the Sphinx Temple...
the North Lodge...
an E-W orientation...
where it passes the...
at the end of the...
Sphinx Temple...
at the 18th Dynasty...
by a small...
the Amun...
encountered...
frank R2...
cleared a shelf of...
quartz...
shelf of...
the Sphinx...
about 2 m...
The... of the...

Terrace II

- Intro.
- Edge unfinished
 - N Ledge
 - W Causeway
- Floor
 - Before paving - pavement
 - Levelling
 - Unfinished
 - Major Fault
 - Member I-II interface channel
 - NE Cuttings
 - Holes - or in SE
 - Keystone Shaft

TERRACE II: THE SPHINX SANCTUARY

The Sphinx sits in a U-shaped ditch, open to the east, that has been called the Sphinx Sanctuary. The ~~sanctuary~~ ^{ancient} ~~was created~~ builders ^{quarried} ~~created~~ the sanctuary out of the natural rock while leaving a core - probably in the form of a long rectangular block - which they sculpted into the Sphinx's lion-body.

Perimeter

The outline of the Sphinx ditch gives a clear indication of where work stopped before it was completely cut to its intended dimensions. ~~The~~

The north side of the sanctuary is a continuation to the west of the North Ledge that begins more than 45 m out in front of the Sphinx Temple. As described above, this ledge limits Terrace I on the north and runs past the Sphinx Temple north wall. Along this part the face of the North Ledge is well cut and fairly straight on an E-W orientation. The face of the ledge is still well-cut when it passes the rise to Terrace II (at elevation 10.59) at the west end of the corridor between the N ledge and Sphinx Temple. The ledge passes under the SE corner of the 18 Dynasty ^{red brick} Amenhotep II Temple. Here it is covered by a small mound of debris that supports this corner of the Amenhotep II Temple. - In 1978 Hawari and Lehner excavated stratigraphic trenches into this deposit. Their trench R2, just below the Amenhotep II temple entrance cleared a shelf of natural rock that was left when quarry ~~work~~ ^{to form} on the North Ledge was abandoned. The shelf of uncut rock is 4 m wide and 1.10 m high off the Sphinx Sanctuary floor. The shelf ~~is~~ is cut down about 2.11 from the top of the North Ledge (Terrace III). The top surface of the rock shelf rises in height, and

narrower in width, toward the west to merge with the intended line of the North Ledge as it passes the length of the Sphinx sanctuary. While this higher 'intended line' becomes somewhat irregular, it generally ~~lines up~~ ^{E-W line of the} ~~E-W~~ with, and continues the ledge from out in front of the Sphinx Temple. During the Hawass-Lehner 1978 excavations, ^{the} ~~the~~ surface of the unfinished shelf, ~~was~~ carefully cleaned. The surface ~~is~~ ^{has} ~~characterized~~ ^{covered with} by ~~the~~ square-ish ~~lumps~~ protrusions and "channels" characteristic of the way in which stone was worked away ^{from top-down} in ancient Egypt. The channels were filled with compact sand and gypsum that contained crude tools in chert, one with oxidized copper stains, and Old Kingdom crude red ware sherds. — bits and pieces of the Sphinx builder's utensils.

It is evident that the ledge ~~was~~ being built by workers who were working the ledge down both from the top and ^{laterally} from the east to west. ~~the~~ when they abandoned their edge of the Sphinx sanctuary.

At the west end of the sanctuary, behind the Sphinx's tail, the work was left in an even cruder, more preliminary stage. It was probably the intention of the builders to strike a 90° corner from the north to the west edge of the ditch, and to cut the west edge back to the face of the higher ledge behind the Sphinx. But the west side was left as an ~~irregular~~ irregular ^{massive} mass of stone jutting out ~~to~~ ^{to} leave only 2.60 m ^{clearance to} the Sphinx rump. The west edge rises about 4.5 m from the sanctuary floor (to Terrace III).

The south side of the Sphinx Sanctuary strikes an angle of 13°41' to the E-W orientation of the Sphinx and to the N edge of the ditch. This is the angle (south of east) of the Khafre Pyramid causeway. The last 100 m of the ^{embankment} ~~causeway~~ ^{foundation} is it

of the floor must have followed closely the cutting back of the edges of the ditch, for the floor is level right up to the unfinished face of the North ledge. However, just at the rear of the statue, by the ramp, ~~that~~ the place where levelling work stopped ~~is apparent~~ as it progressed from east to west is apparent. The ancient quarrymen were working, at all stages of stone removal and dressing, ^{from SE to NW} into the slope dip or slope of the rock strata which is NW to SE. They ~~some~~ ~~had~~ ~~found~~ ~~it~~ ~~was~~ proceeded in like fashion for the much larger work of levelling the terrace around the Khafre Pyramid.

South Channel

There are several prominent features in the floor of the Sphinx sanctuary. ~~A kind of shallow channel~~ ~~the floor~~ There is a broad and shallow depression in the floor just beside the ~~South~~ large coisson (stone box) attached to the south side of the Sphinx. This depression narrows to form a kind of channel, up to 50 cm deep, that runs ^{eastward} roughly parallel to the South forepaw. ~~For~~ At a point about opposite the front of the forepaw, the channel begins to phase out as it curves toward the southeast. The channel is a natural feature. It marks the contact of the upper Member II geological layers — ~~over~~ with the lower Member I stone. These geological layers all dip through the Sphinx and its site from NW to SE. The depression and channel are where the floor ^{Sanctuary} cuts the meeting of Member I and II. The first layer of Member II (Bed I) is a very soft marly limestone. This has weathered away on the floor to leave the channel.

X. Major Fissure

There are many fine fissures running through the sanctuary floor. A series of these come together to form what I have called the Major Fissure. It runs through the

whole body of the Sphinx and its sanctuary. It can be traced ~~seen~~ from the top of the Khafre causeway on the south side of the ditch, along the south floor to the south hind paw, and through the entire exposed bedrock core-body of the statue. It continues on the north floor where it opens into a crack about 1 m long and 30 cm wide. This opening was exposed during the 1978 SRI International cleaning in the Sphinx sanctuary. It was filled w/ sand and rubble. ~~The~~^{It} was partially cleared this fill on April 29, 1978 during work in the sanctuary under the direction of Dr. Zahi Hawass, ~~The rubble fill was~~^a to a depth of 1.30 m. The fill consisted of brown or grey dirt-sand mixture with limestone fragments. Charcoal flecks, a few pottery fragments, and spots of damp clay or mud indicated that this fill was culturally deposited. It appeared that the crack had not been cleared during previous modern excavations. All the pottery was saved, and the mud spots, carbon flecks, and soil matrix were sampled. These materials are stored in the E.A.O. magazine west of the Great Pyramid. Excavation could proceed no farther due to the narrowness of the space. At this depth, the fill still contained carbon flecks and pottery fragments. On February 11, 1979 I visited the site just after three days of hard rain. The rain left considerable amounts of water standing in depressions here and there in the floor of the Sphinx sanctuary. In the crack the rubble fill had apparently collapsed, as now the crack looked to be open to a depth of 3 or 4 m. I examined this opening again during the first season of the ARCE Sphinx Project on July 7 and 11, 1979. ~~At~~ I had myself lowered down, ~~the~~ head first, into the fissure with a flashlight ~~that~~ that I held out before me. The crack appeared to extend nearly 5 m under floor level.

At the bottom it narrowed to a width of a few centimeters and it appeared to angle to the east. ~~Sections of pipe were fastened to~~ I fastened together sections of pipe and pushed the pipe down into the fissure to a depth of 5 m. At about 4.5 m the soil was quite wet, indicating the level of ground water. ~~The opening was closed with large limestone pieces.~~

Holes and Rectangular Cuttings

Here and there in the sanctuary floor are small ^{square} rectangular cuttings and artificial holes. These have yet to be ~~systematically~~ ^{completely} mapped. In the floor of the SE corner of the Sanctuary, alongside the ^{back} wall of the Sphinx Temple, ~~there~~ small holes, about 10 cm in diameter, ~~are~~ occur in rows at regular spacings of a little more than a meter. ~~In the NE corner of the sanctuary, as a concentrated series of the square~~ ^{1979 I excavated} ~~rectangular cuttings and small holes was~~ ~~For~~ I excavated ^{and mapped} a concentrated series of the rectangular cuttings and small holes in the NE corner of the sanctuary as a ~~part~~ follow-up to the 1978 excavations of the larger deposit in that corner. The association of these features with large core blocks abandoned during the building of the Sphinx Temple strongly suggests they were for ~~ropes~~ ^{levels and ropes} (on pegs in the holes) ~~for~~ used in moving the multi-tonned blocks. The full discussion of the NE corner features in the floor belongs with the report of the excavations there. Additional series of the rectangular cuttings - probably level sockets, occur off the north flank of the Sphinx and in the NW corner of the sanctuary.

Keystone Shaft

There is a square shaft cut into the floor of the Sphinx and slightly in and under the North Ledge just opposite the North Third Row. The shaft was cleared during the 1978 excavations of Hawass in the Sphinx area.

It has never been published.

It was not entirely clear whether the shaft had been excavated previously by Hassan or Barozze. The sand and debris ~~around the~~ ~~led~~ banked up against the N-Ledge enough to cover the opening before the 1978 clearing. An irregular shallow trench, with characteristic ~~random~~ ~~chaotic~~ ~~quarry~~ channels and ridges, was cut ~~at~~ into the floor along the face of the ledge to either side of the shaft - probably just before the shaft itself was cut. The trench runs 4 m south of ~~the shaft~~ and 6.20 m north of the shaft for a total length of 12 m. The shaft itself measures ~~1.42~~ ^{1.42} (E-W) by 1.06 (N-S). ^{and is about 2 m deep} At the top of the shaft on the face of the ledge there is a cutting like ~~an~~ ^{up} the bottom of a keystone hole upside down. This led me to dub the ~~shaft~~ ^{whole} feature "the Keystone Shaft." A fissure runs from the SE corner of the shaft over to the N (third Pass), and up through the N Ledge. The fill of the trench contained a few sherds and mudspots spots of packed mud. The latter could be mudbrick which fell from the midwall (built by TIV?) that ran along the top of the ledge, a section of which still remains just to the west of the shaft. Mostly the fill was ~~gyp~~ ^{sandy} rubble ~~with~~ limestone fragments, under a layer of whiter more gypsiferous material. Just above the shaft there was a large square locally quarried limestone boulder resting on this debris, along with other smaller but fair-sized ~~pieces~~ ^{pieces} of limestone and chunks of mortar. On the east edge of the shaft, under 50 cm of rubble, there was a limestone block of one side angled ~~like~~ which may be a piece of mastaba casing. The fill around this was sandy ^{with} fine gravel lenses characteristic of water sorting - probably deposited ~~during rains~~ ^{by rain water}. Among other large pieces of limestone, ^{at the far east end of the trench,} was ~~at~~ the top of a lotus-design limestone offering stand cut in a lotus-design. X

The trench cuts into either side of the shaft ~~at~~ the rim of which is at floor level ~~the~~ high than the trench.

It varies from 20-30 cm in width and it is about 20 cm deep.

Multiple wet lines with water sorted
Trenches fill - objects
Bottom shaft fill - Top here

The bottom of the trench, with the quarry hump and depression, was ~~clean~~ ^{white} and exposed for any length of time.

In the shaft itself, under the upper layer of rubble

There was clean sand, followed by sand and limestone rubble. The latter deposit contained a large piece of basalt (ca. $30 \times 40 \times 50$ cm) w/ ~~one~~ ^{one} side possibly finished one finished side. This rested on a layer of ~~compact dark~~ ~~red~~ sand w/ mud spots that phased into black compact mud & mounding up in the ~~SE~~ ^{SW} corner of the shaft.

The mud was about 60 cm over the bottom of the shaft ~~underneath~~. It proved to be about 4 to 10 cm thick and it phased into a tan clayey mud-sand mixture, and finally to compact sand w/ ~~mud~~ spots of clay and charcoal flecks.

The shaft is probably an unfinished tomb. The narrow track to either side is an unfinished effort to deepen the floor at the front of the tomb. ~~at the door~~ This is what was done in the front of the unfinished tomb before the NE corner of the Sphinx Temple. The fill of the shaft contained no modern inclusions, indicating this feature may have been overlooked in previous excavations here. The fill is characteristic of ~~alternating~~ cycles of wind blown sand, ^{and} erosion off mudbrick walls, and finally ~~the fill~~ which ran above the shaft along the top of the N-Ledge.

Sound and Light Channels

Several channels for cables belonging to the "Sound and Light Show" system ~~have~~ ^{was} been cut into the sanctuary floor. The most prominent of these is 11 cm wide and 17 cm deep. ~~The most p~~ It begins at the cement ^{lamp} box opposite box for housing lamps opposite the North forepaw and runs in a straight line to the NW corner of the sanctuary. Here it turns 90° to run straight N-S to the SW corner, where it turns 90° again to run straight E-W to ^{ward} another sound and light lamp box opposite the south elbow of the Sphinx. The channel does not quite reach the ^{south} lamp box but phases

out at the broad depression that narrows to the natural channel in the floor of the south side described above.

There are some square ~~cutting~~ holes alongside this channel at the east end of the north line. ~~I would not have been~~ Apparently the channel and these holes were never used by the Sound and Light system. From the appearance of these features I would not have been certain they were modern. However, Reis Mohammed Abd al Mawjud, longtime employee of the Antiquities Service, remembers when they were cut ~~at the~~ when the S+L system was installed in the early 1960's. Other, shallower channels cross the sanctuary floor diagonally in both the NE and SE corners. These ^{are for} carried ~~out~~ cables to lamp boxes in those areas. Another prominent ^{cable} channel runs N-S parallel to the Sphinx Temple wall in the SE corner of the sanctuary.

TERRACE III: "THE SPHINX AMPHITHEATER"

Terrace III is the open surface north of the Sphinx sanctuary and ~~at~~ north of the Sphinx Temple. It is ^{that I have called the} bounded on the north by the higher ^{NORTH} cliff ledge or cliff ~~which~~ ^{and beyond} above ^{sanctuary of the Khufu Pyramid} which is the Eastern ~~End of~~ ^{of tombs - Reisner's} Cemetery, G7000. Terrace III is bounded on the west by the high ledge that ~~can~~ runs from the Khafre causeway embankment to the modern road. On the south Terrace III is limited by the North Ledge ^{of the Sphinx sanctuary} which drops to Terrace II ^{further east,} of ~~the Sphinx Sanctuary~~ and to Terrace I of the Sphinx Temple. There is a bit of Terrace III, ^{about 4.6 to 9.3 m. wide,} behind the Sphinx. As mentioned ~~and~~ in the description of Terrace II, ~~the intention had~~ ~~po~~ ~~there~~ ~~had~~ probably there had been the intention to quarry this back to the higher ledge, and this bit was left unfinished. ~~The surface of the~~ Terrace III is not, strictly speaking, a "terrace" The

area within these boundaries, with the addition of the Sphinx sanctuary and ^{Terrace I with} the Sphinx Temple, Hassan called the Sphinx "Amphitheater."

Terrace III is not, strictly speaking, a "terrace." This surface slopes from a high point of 22.50 m (31.83 m.s.l.) at the far NW corner formed by Terrace IV and the modern road, to 14.0 ^(23.33 m.s.l.) at the NE corner of the Sphinx sanctuary, and to 12.14 ^(21.47 m.s.l.) opposite the NE corner of the Sphinx Temple. The total slope ^{of Terrace III} within the Sphinx "amphitheater" then, is better than 10 m. As indicated by the contour intervals on the map (Fig. —), the slope is not particularly even. This surface is actually ^{even} ~~more~~ ~~than~~ ~~irregular~~ irregular than indicated by the .50 m contour intervals. Within the slope, the surface is characterized by small hummocks, and ~~troughs~~ ^{troughs} and basins, giving a 1 to 2 m of relief. The small hummocks are ~~either~~ sponges formed from ^{fossilized} aggregates of sponges, corals, oysters and possibly stromatolites (laminated mound-like sediments produced by algae) on ~~the~~ a shallow reef of the Eocene sea waters ca. 50 million years ago. The troughs and basins, with a fine grain stone, are ^{scaped} low areas between ~~and~~ the bioaggregation of the hummocks. The remarkable thing about Terrace III is that ~~the~~ its surface is that of ~~the~~ a ^{fossilized} shallow reef ~~is~~ nearly in life position. More will be said ^{in the next chapter.} of the geology in this specific area. For now, it can be ~~most~~ pointed out that this fact is possible because the rock from the surface of Terrace III downwards ^{is} extremely hard and brittle ^{(Member I) the higher rock} while ~~the~~ which was quarried away to form Terrace III is much softer (Member II). The first layer overlying the rock of Terrace III ~~is~~ is a particularly soft yellow clay-like stone (Bed 1). Thus the ancient quarrymen were able to strip off the overlying rock, ^{across Terrace III} ~~to~~ while leaving

PART ONE: THE SPHINX IN THE OLD KINGDOM

- INTRODUCTION
- 1. • HISTORY of Research
- 2. • Geographic Context
- 3. • Setting within the Giza Plateau
 - Geomorphology
 - Architectural
- 4. • Sphinx Site - Khafre Valley Complex
 - Terraces
 - I, II, III, IV
 - Geology of the Terraces
 - Quarrying the Terraces
 - and: Left a core for Sphinx statue, segue to next chap.
- Sphinx Core Body
- Masonry, Veneer / Carvings
- Stratigraphy of the Chapel
- The Valley Temple
- The Sphinx Temple
- Summary and Conclusions

PART TWO: THE SPHINX IN LATER ANTIQUITY

- Robbing of the Sphinx Temple
- 18th Dynasty Complex
- Late N.K. to Classical Times

The natural ~~deposit~~ plane of deposition of the shoal reef, as it was deposited 50 ~~to~~ million years ago.

The ^{cultural} deposits overlying Terrace III were the principle focus of Hassans excavations in 1936. Over the centuries, a tremendous amount of debris and drift sand had accumulated. Yet there must have been periods when the surface of Terrace III was at least partially clear since there are remnants of three ancient structures from times later than the Sphinx founded upon its surface.

~~NP~~ Just off the NE corner of the Sphinx ditch is the ruined Amenhotep II temple to Horus-Horemakhet. The axis of this temple is oriented 0° E of N so that its entrance is directed toward the head of the Sphinx.

The SE corner of the Amenhotep Temple ~~overlaps the~~ extends across the corridor ^{on the} north the Sphinx Temple to overlap the ~~corner~~ ^{NW corner} of the Sphinx Temple.

The overlapping corner of the midbrick temple is actually sited upon a displaced locally quarried core block intended for the Sphinx Temple. One could suggest that the Amenhotep II Temple is so positioned to take advantage of the firm ground of Terrace III. We know that, at the time of A II, the Sphinx Temple was stripped of its finish alabaster paving and granite sheathing, ~~and~~ and it lay in ruins buried under debris. A II could have built his temple over these ruins, upon the ~~compact debris fill~~ unless the fill of the Sphinx Temple was mostly loose sand.

However, there may have been a thematic as well as a practical reason for the orientation of the later temple. Its gateway points to the sun setting over the Sphinx's head at the winter solstice. Two other temples of Horus-as-the-Horus ~~as-the-Horus~~ one-of-the-Horus likewise show an ~~orientation~~ orientation to the solstices. At any rate, this area of Terrace III was cleared when ~~the~~ Amenhotep II's temple

LATER

41

The large midbrick wall on Terrace II was also part of an architectural arrangement in front of four tombs cut into the Western ledge at the NW corner of the Sphinx 'amphitheater'. These were first cleared by Cavignac in 1816 and described by Birch ().

The arrangement included flights of steps leading to platforms built up to extend from the fronts of the tombs. Of the four, — have been identified as belonging to — (These) and the ^{entire} group of four appear to be saite, 26th Dynasty.

Another series of ^{south-facing} tombs is located in the North Cliff that rises some 7 to 10 m above the average level of Terrace III.

Hasson, who cleared these tombs in 1936, noted that the 14 tombs he counted occurred in two levels. (Hasson 1960, 5). He suggested that the ^{higher} tombs were cut into the cliff at a time when the base of the cliff was covered by sand. — This was ^{at least as early as} the New Kingdom since some of the higher tombs had New Kingdom ~~reliefs~~ relief carving and graffiti. The lower level tombs are Old Kingdom; three were inscribed and belonged to Ankh Ra, Kai Ahmose, and Inka f.

Today, some of these tombs are blocked up, or concealed by modern buildings belonging to the Sound and Light system, the modern road that descends from the Khufu Pyramid down across the face of the cliff, or the down embankment on which this road is founded. The road leads to

CONT

Hasson observed that most of the tombs appear to have been left uncompleted.

was founded. Was this part of the Sphinx clearing alluded to by the son of AII, Thutmose IV on his stela erected at the base of the Sphinx's chest?

➔ About 60 m west of the entrance to the AII Temple there is a section of mudbrick wall, 8.14 m long, still standing on the edge of the North Ledge of the Sphinx sanctuary. It ~~was~~ apparently ^{is} ~~but~~ part of a series of walls built by TIV around the site to hold back drift sand. ~~This~~ ^{This section} is partly founded on small limestone ~~slab~~ slabs which AII & crosses in the N. Ledge that is part of the Major Fissure crossing the Sphinx sanctuary.

A larger mudbrick wall, 4.07 m thick and 24.79 m long still stands perpendicular to the ^{western} back ledge of the Sphinx 'amphitheater'. It is also founded on the rock surface of Terrace III. The masonry appearance and slightly better on the face of this wall suggest it was part of a late ^{possibly Saite} enclosure wall around the whole Valley Complex. Another section of a similarly sized wall, running E-W in front of the Sphinx Temple is seen in Arch. Lacau photo . Here, however, the wall appears to be situated high up upon cultural debris and ^{wind blown} sand filling the area in front of the Sphinx Temple.

A series of ~~Saite~~ ^{Saite} [?] tombs ^{0.15} located in the west ledge at the NW corner of Terrace III. These were already cleared by Cavillig in 1876 and described by Birch

Although Harvan (1953, fig. 1) labels it as part of the protective walls built by Thutmose II. Some of the enclosure walls around the site certainly were identified by stamping as having been built by Thutmose II, but it is doubtful that this wall was one of them.

Complete

HASSAN, Excavations Vol. IX (1960) p. 5

N CLIFF

2 Levels of 14 Rock-hewn tombs

3 inscribed

1. K3; whmw

2. Ah-Rc

3. In-K3.f

CONT.

The ~~modern road~~ ~~remains~~ descending from the Khufu Pyramid to the ~~Soudan~~ parking area and town of Naqat es-Samaan, ~~runs~~ ~~across~~ the ~~north~~ side of Terrace III. Parallel to the road immediately south of it ^{along the south side of} there is a modern wall that was built to above headheight of the average person.

The Sphinx side of this wall descends to the rock surface of Terrace III, while the ^{other} side ~~is~~ is based on the ~~bed~~ debris bedding of the road.

The opposite, north side of the road is also sanded in up to the North Cliff, or to retaining walls in front of the tombs in this cliff.

~~These tombs all date to the Old Kingdom~~

I surveyed the ^{tomb} entrances in the North Cliff that were visible in 1981. The points I located were used to add Hassan's tomb interiors and those tombs since concealed to my overall site map (Fig.). I count 18 tombs, combining upper and lower levels, and Hassan's site map (1960) with my 1981 survey data.

TERRACE IV

Terrace IV is the ~~top~~ surface at the top of the Western Lodge of the Sphinx ("Amphitheater") and the Khafre Causeway foundation that limits the Sphinx sanctuary and amphitheater on the south. This surface is, again, not a true terrace; ~~but a slope~~ It slopes from elevation 29.0 (38.33 M.S.L.) at the NW corner of the Western Cliff of the modern road to 21.5 (30.83 M.S.L.) at the ^{SW} corner of the Sphinx amphitheater, Western Cliff with the Khafre causeway. The surface of the ^{shoulder of the} causeway ~~should~~ slopes

29.00
9.33
38.33

21.500
9.331
30.831

Complete

DREAM NOTES

"I spent 6 years"

Matakh

N side - Zaki trench cut in floor - "Mural" - "to the floor of the Sphinx" - Abd al Samih - Zaki looking at all large caisson - almost dismantled - passage found - punch report - "don't show him" - Go in; to S side to see body - other people, vertical shaft, tunnel, placed spiral metal stairway, down (not too far?)

1920: 200
Mad
era Pitti
sticker

Divergence, reminder to come back, passage wide, goes on - emerges into characteristic Member I, emerges E end N corridor, My a table case,

patch
in tubed
in
rock
floor

chewed on jelly, cheese sandwiches and Sphinx material that would have been lost; back inside room, under debris on floor, walk over large tree - "used whole tree for leverage?" Specific club of Faruk

Thir all known? Be back to clear up rubble, map.

Hassan Sphinx p. 32, Fig. 16 debris ca. 20 ft high
over floor level of AII temple; debris against
North cliff - Pl. XX

Pl. XXVIII, Fig. 34, p. 47 and text pp 37-8. Annex to front
W end of temple indicates habitation on Terrace
III late after TIV (re-use of one of his
stolae in walls, also door posts of Set II
re-used as floor slabs in Room 3 of AII
Temple

Sphinx

NOTE — N. Hind paw looks to have been finished in Member I - (smoothed w/ plaster fill?). While S. hind paw built of Phase I-type blocks due to dip of Member I stone to South. So originally Sphinx half built of Phase I (Ia?) masonry and half completed in Bedrock? Bedrock = head N. hind paw, lower front elbows, etc.? Did they (4th Dynasty) cut back Member II and build upon Member I leaving lower profile in Member I?

INSERT

Was this part of the Sphinx clearing attributed to by the son of Amenhotep II, Thutmose IV, on his stela erected at the base of the Sphinx's chest?

On the other hand, Hassan's ^{final site} map shows, immediately to the northeast of the Amenhotep II, another structure of similar ground plan, size and orientation.

He ^{elsewhere (1958, 67)} identifies this structure as the "mudbrick temple of Thutmose I (?)" ~~giving~~ giving a completely different ground plan (Ibid., fig 60) than that on his site plans (Ibid. Pl. XVI; 1960, fold out map).

There is, ~~at~~ in any case, ^{other} evidence as well that indicates Terrace II may have been partially clear of sand ~~before~~ at the ~~beginning~~ earlier in the 18th Dynasty.

INTRODUCTION

CHAP 1 Topographical and Geological Setting.

CHAP 2 History of Archaeological Research

CHAP 4 The Sphinx Site: Khafre Valley Complex

A. Terraces

B. Geology of Terraces

C. Quarrying of Terraces

CHAP 3 The ARCE Sphinx Project.
(Goals, control grid, etc.)

CHAP 5 The Sphinx Core Body

- Geology

- Topological Description

CHAP 6 The Masonry Veneer

CHAP 7 Passages

CHAP 8 CHAPEL

CHAP 9 Sphinx as Sculpture

- Cubit Grid

- Compare to Sphinx canon

- Compare to "Classic" Sphinx

- Compare to O.K. Sculpture

- Sphinx as prototype

Terrace IV (cont.)

The modern road embankment, at the NW corner of the Sphinx amphitheater is actually slightly higher than Terrace IV here. Modern steps lead from the shoulder of the road down to Terrace IV.

The bedrock surface of Terrace IV behind the Sphinx is itself a kind of roadway or causeway sloping from the Khafre causeway up toward the north. There is a large trapezoidal-shaped area behind the Sphinx, defined by the Khafre causeway as it slopes up to the Khafre Mortuary Temple, the southern side of the Khafre Pyramid and ~~the~~ ^{Mastaba field} GI-5, and the embankment for the modern

450 x
200

Get

Mariette Le Serapeum de Memphis
Maspero Deuxieme rapport
Grebaut Service des Antiquités

p. 10. Sphinx built after 18th Dynasty
found by Grebaut during his work

p. 11. Sphinx similar, well completed in
18th Dynasty

p. 12. Terrace I, II, III, IV, V, VI, VII, VIII
and IX complex

Landings above for houses used in 18th
and 19th Dynasty

p. 14. No longer existing, once finished

p. 15. Pylons to lower terrace at 18th
Dynasty

p. 16. Cairo papyrus in 3rd floor
Lithic in middle of 18th Dynasty
not found before work stopped
No more found individual papyrus
stone in any ground level

p. 17. Ceiling in terrace and entrance door

Documents 2 vols = 1883 n 1864, 1865

Ricke Harmachistempel

p. 9-10: Wrong reasons for Khafre to ~~se~~ site his Valley Temple to SE as opp. to axis E-W of Pyramid.

p. 10.
p. 4 Sphinx built after V.T., Causeway finished, begun during their construction

p. 11.
4 W sides Sphinx ^{terrace} sanctuary never completed on N and

p. 4. Terraces I, II, at angle to ~~each other~~ E-W axis of complex

Limestone Blocks from terraces used in V.T. and M.T. of Khafre

p. 4 N Ledge cutting, never finished

p. 5-6 Perpendicular - to Lower Terrace axis points to Sphinx head

p. 6 - Canical protrusions in S.T. floor
[M.L. - I wonder if much of floor was ever paved before work was stopped.
No "seats" for individual pavement slabs as in Pyramid Courts]

p. 7 - Casing on exterior around entrance doors only.

DOORWAYS

3 cubits

≈

1.575 m

MT ST

Abb 4, 5

Statues of S.T., M.T Robbed out for reuse, Holscher obs. (fnt 28).

p. 13

ENTRANCE DOORS - planned as 3 cubits wide 1.575 widened to 2 cubits during const. of S.T. 2.10

Note

Center Socket to Center Socket on TIV Stela Backside is 1.15 m. Matches Socket - Socket Measurement on Grand plan of V.T. entrance, to vestibule - other doorways more 1.20 m. But all V.T. door lintels intact except entrances - would these have been wider? Probably, like Ricker's S.T. entrances, about 2.10 or wider (4 cubits +). TIV Stela would be reused lintel to inner rooms just inside S.T. or M.T entrance door a 1.20 m

HOLSCHER

elevation
Holscher Blatt VIII
V.T. ^{outer} Doors = 2.27 m. wide accord. to his scale

Main Entrance Doorways pp. 40-41

Main MT door = 8 mm = 1.34 m wide

59.5 mm = 10 m
1 m = .168 m

1.20

BLATT XVIII

Entrance Door

V.T. = 2.32

Vestibule Entrances

V.T. = 8 mm x .15 = 1.20 m

V.T. Plan
100 mm = 15 m
1 mm = .15 m

Door Pivot Sockets pp. 44-45
Abb. 29. 30

Note Ricke 5
Abb. C' • Front entrance doors, only
single door - single floor socket
• Doorways to cult niches double
but too wide
• Doorway to S Ambulatory
single - single pivot hole in floor
• Only doorway can be (TIV
Stela) is that to N Ambulatory

p. 16 - entrances to Court - 3 cubits 1.575 m

p. 20 S.T. North Corridor "wooden ceiling" traces
are actually groove for splitting core block
in two down middle

p. 22 Pillars 8 cubits high - like those in V.T.
off alabaster floor
+ Architraves 2 m high
= 10 cubits 5.25 m
Niches 2 cubits lower Fig. 13

p. 23. Core blocks of 3rd course are highest course

p. 25 S.T. Completely captured when robbed of
finish stone.

2 Robbing Periods 1. Amenemhat I (to List)
2. V.T. Robbed

No traces of large statues

↓ edge 130 indicated
Chapel planned in Old Kingdom

RICKE HARMACHISTEMPEL

p. 25 Standing statues excluded - because base too long - stats. would have been too high.

p. 26. Reconstruction of entrance doors - uncertain

Doors 2.10 m wide Abb. 15
Original (?) width $\approx$ 1.5 m wide

Reconstruction of the Temple
Reconstruction of the Temple
Reconstruction of the Temple
Band
Statue
Wall
Base

* Ledge 136 indicates
Chapel planned in Old Kingdom

CONCLUDING

- Building the Sphinx — Terraces left large rectangle
 - Vailey Temple — Stage 1
 - Vailey Temple Stage 2
 - Sphinx Temple
 - Ditch
 - Sphinx statue

- Left incomplete — ditch
- Sphinx left incomplete

- Robbed and Abandoned

- Reconstructed — 18th Dynasty

- Theoretical Reconstruction

Beard
Statue
Views
Face

37975
3.79 ha

35275
3.52 ha

Fig. 1.1

1.2.

1.3

1.4

1.5

Map of Egypt

Map of Giza Plateau

Map of E, S. Fields w/ Naz. Sam

Map of Sphinx w/ Modern installations
in front, Grid Coordinate System

Geological Profile - Aigner

Fig. 1.1 Map of Egypt

Fig. 1.2 Map of Giza Plateau

Fig. 1.3 Reconstruction of Plateau

Fig. 1.4 Aigner Profile

Khafre - Great Statue
builder

Cemetery to South
of Causeway

V.T.s in diagonal

Khafre

V.T.

Causeway

P.T - Court imp

Court

Cemetery in Central Field
away

(Point of Cemetery to South
Empty to North)

- w.c.f.?

Sphinx as part of
Khafre Valley Complex

S.T.

NOTE Axis - Angle of
Lower Terrace orients
observer of Sphinx to
Pyramid in background
Later axis of S.T
orients E-W to
Equinox

- Granite preserved to
original wall height
- Statues
- Corridor to Causeway
- Circuit
- Causeway NW corner
articulation

Royal Precincts

V
S

Swing over
to Valley
Complex

Alignment w/
South side
Khafre

Intro - Imp. of
V.T. to Sphinx T.
Sphinx.

Global fall in sea level at
end of Eocene causes sea
regression Aigner "Facies" p. 364

ORIGINS OF GIZA PLATEAU

Middle Eocene

Aigner "Facies"
(Aigner Forthcoming)

1. Pyramids paleohigh from Late Cretaceous tectonism
- Submarine swell

"A topographic
high
presumably
by storm
events" p. 361

2. Massive nummulitic packstones on northern Pyramids

Plateau "banks" - Forms barrier } Equinoidal
Blown and sorted by storm waves } accumulation
winnowing away their home muds } nummulite
coquina

3. Deeper back bank environment

4. True reefal environment grows up over bank slope
shoal reef including patches of coral
Nward dev. to shoal facies

→ Clear, subtropical shallow environment of deposition

Correspondences

Khafre Causeway slope

Sphinx - 3 parts

Shoal Reef facies

"Reef growth in
irregular patches"

→ NWARD
interfinger with

Shoal facies

BACK BANK

p. 361

"Lower energy environment"

quieter protected waters

lagoonal p. 364

Architectural Context

Chapter 1

Chapter 2 Layout of Giza Necrop. is determined by 3

Pyramid Complexes

Chapter 3

Introduction

Chap. 1 - Context

Chap. 2 - History of Research

Chap. 3. Terraces

Chap. 4

Egyptian Archaeology

OCT 1

DEC 6-7 Reading Period.

1. OCT 2
2. OCT 4
3. OCT 9
4. OCT 11
5. OCT 16
6. OCT

Upper Egypt

Book of the Dead

Amarna

El-Amarna

Amarna

Amarna

Sakel Amarna

KANTOR BASICS

- Geological - Cultural Periods to Neolithic
- Paleolithic - latest understanding, summary
- Predynastic

Lower Egypt

Fayum A
Merimde
Maadi
el-Amari

Upper Egypt

Badarian
Amratian
Gerzean

I. ART

Pallettes
Gebel Arak Knife

II. Hieroglyphs

III. Architecture

Beginning of Codification

- Archaic

Codification

DYN I

Saggaras Tombs
Abydos Tombs
Abydos vs. Saggaras
Smaller Tombs, Abu Roash, Helwan

Dynasty II

Abydos } Royal
Saggaras }
Saggaras Private
Nag'ed-Deir

Dynasty III

Tombs private { Beit Khallaf
Mastaba I
Hesyrre
Zawiyet Arian
Zawiyet Ma'adin
Djoser Step Pyramid
Sekhemkhet

Jump to 7th Dyn in Allen Notes

Codification

Codification

- 4th Dynasty
Sneferu Pyramids
South, North Dakhur; Meidum
- Giza
3 Pyramid Complexes
Temple development
- Zawiyet el Aryan, Mastabat Faroun
- Private Tombs
Meidum: Rahotep
Giza: Development, internalization of chapel,
Mastaba to rock cut
- False Door development
- Dynasty V Pyramid Complexes & Sun Temples
- Private Mastabas - Dyn. V, Saggara Ti, Akh-hotep
Unas rock cut, etc.
- Giza
- Dyn. VI Mastabas: Unas causeway & Teti Pyramid
Giza Small Private Tombs
Pyramid Complexes
- Provincial Tombs, Dyn. II-V-VI
& More on False Doors
- Old Kingdom Provincial Temples
Abydos
Hierakonpolis

- First Intermediate Period

Break in royal monuments, line of continuity in private tombs

Pr
segmentation
local
hierarchies

Moalla

Saqqara

Heracléopolis (check archaeology of)

- Dyn. XI

I. Royal Tombs - Thebes

A. Nag el-Tarif 11th Dyn. Nubkheper Intef; SAKF Tombs

B. Deir el-Bahri - Mentuhotep

II. Private Tombs

A. Thebes (Mentuhotep Cemetery)

1. Courtiers Tombs

a. shaft type

b. catacomb type

2. Deir Assasif

3. Deir el Bahri

4.

5. Abd el-Qurna

- Dynasty XII

I. Royal Tombs

II. Private Tombs

III. Religious Architecture

A. Standard - Qasr es-Sagha

B. Back Temples

C. Pterial Temples

D. Rock cut Temples

E. Mortuary Temples Senusert III Abdas

Second Intermediate Period

- I. Royal Tombs - Thebes
- II. Royal Tombs - Saggara
- III. "Hyksos Towns"
 - ① Tell Yahudiya
 - ② Tell el-Daba

- NEW KINGDOM - Mortuary

- I. Royal Mortuary Temples; TII-III to RIII
 - II. Mortuary Temples - private
 - III. Royal Tombs
 - A. Dra Abu Naga - AI?
 - B. Biban el Maluk TI (1438) earliest
 - C. Valley of Queens
 - D. Cenotaphs
 - E. Typology
Tomb Plan (emic)
 - F. Funerary Chapels
 - G. Scenes and Texts
 - IV Private Tombs
-

ML - New Kingdom Urban

- A. Amarna
- B. Malkata Antecedents
- C. Deir el-Ballas

- New Kingdom Temples

Third Intermediate Period

FIGURES

- 1. MAP OF EGYPT
- 2. MAP OF PYRAMID FIELD

Policy - research
 Arch - practice
 BS - the legal position
 Trans - the
 Project - research
 Research - needs
 Can be achieved - Synthesis
 Radio - memo
 Current faculty 4's
 Identification - needed
 in teaching - were
 Memo - please to the other teachers
 Open to guest - discussion

IT - include all Arts or Archaeology
 MA - Koen Wilson next quarter teaching of art
 EW - Archaeology needed in arts
 Head - history - Syn Selections
 BS - candidates will be anthropological

Priority - direct participation
 Coll - current curriculum
 BS - limit post of limit to
 Coll - Teaching needs
 TB - Unlikely to carry out limit to
 archaeology, also to Arts
 Post - possible fit - Arts dept
 "Missed Link"
 Anthropology

O.J. Meeting
28/xi/90

Intro. M. Lehner

- Policy memoranda

- Arch. position

B.S. — History of position

Tenure — Tom

Provost — request to in. search

Research needs

Comprehensive — Syria/Anatolia

Return Memo

Central faculty #'s

Justification needed

re: teaching NELC

Memo — revise to strengthen teaching case

Open to questions, discussions

JJ — include NE Art or Archaeology

MG — Kaen Wilson next quarter teaching — gap?

EW — Archaeological needed vs. art

Need history — Syria/Palestinian

BS — Candidates will be anthropological

Pivinity School participation

Goldb — Cannot rely upon

BS — Limit pool if limit to

Goldb — Teaching needs

TB — Unfortunate to lose, art hist. to
archaeology, also to Anth.

Best possible fit — Anth dept.

↓
"Missing Link"
w/ Anthropology

Fisher - Backfire - all needs ~~to~~ not met
MG. Res. memo - arch. approach affects
vision of hist. of region, chronology, etc.

EW If not teach hist. of region - don't want him

DP - Dept. & OI policy need be established
policy statement

MG If push thru - easier to get funding

JJ Not just Israelite history

JJ - Major interest - actively working in Syria
Material Culture

BS Job description - specific
Justify position to fill chink

Need Accord

Regional criteria

Not too much on methodological etc. issues

Phase 1 Justify search

Phase 2 Selected ind appointed

quality will carry day

Beef up teaching aspects - broad parameter
Beef up

Research itself is teaching matter - vigorous field

Don't neglect - too big opportunity

DP - Dean Cassett said - get me documentation
Cover memo - will attach

~~BS~~

MR Talk to Rob Nelson in Art Dept.

Joint backing

MG - Looking for arch who is a historian

MR - Doesn't hurt to talk to Tom Best

BS - Can't write a job descrip that'd allow

Art Co-sponsorship

Mustache - two diff things

- BS - How resolve?
Mustache - Focus is Syria don't let arch vs art
lose site of CERIA, Ugarit
MG - Aimed at O&I interest - do another memo
aimed at Dept.
BS - Base our memo on points in memo
Teaching - new memo
Agreed
-

Arch. Coordinating Committee

- BS - Skid, Owens, Merrill
Final space diag. / cost est. in week
Go to Pres.
Arch design - next stage
Request \$400,000
Pres. Approves
Un. Arch sends RFPs
Move quickly in selection
Selection Comm. - Present reasoning
Propose: M. Sears
K. Wilson
Visit Comm Member (?)
Un. Arch. Jim Gimple
Faculty?
Early w/ constituency
Mart Stolper
Volunteer?

- DP Faculty offices included?
BS "Dead as demand"
pres. against
Not movable

DP - Need for support space increasing
BS Dd tell her that
Priorities - cut down to Priority 1 set
Other admin. spaces cut
Site design - compatible for future expansion
1 story #6 million
row 4 mill - const costs
2 mill - other

Sponsorship Comm

BS

- + include exhibit suitability
 - + estab. policy, responsibilities
- visit.
lecturer

Rotating Comm

LB

Earlier announcements for OI events

JJ

Exada send info to proposed sponsor?

BS

MS

5 lectures happening at same time
inform
Divisional lecture calendar

BS

- And ME center
Host Look after - Run traffic on it

GLASSES

Establish common OI, MI calendar

BS

Hired someone - will see that this is duty of

* Publication Policy

BS Require or encourage Mss submission in electronic form

Probs gen. 1989 no longer immediate
This covers most issues

3 Member Comm., one rotated off each year
"normally expected"
"strongly encouraged"

JJ 2 points

Resp. of authors for photo publication

MR

Doc. intended for potential authors?

BS Will Make Guidelines for Mss.

MR No publ. Comm now?

BS Submitted to Director

OI Scholar

OI Research

} Dir. makes decision

internal/external reviewers

Result to author

Re submit

Imp to have final vetting

JJ Poor practice - Dir. submitted to one reviewer, Re submit or hire editor

BS Comm to accept on basis of Content

editorial later - "is this kind of work we want to publish?"

Comm deal w each case as they see necessary

MB Act as readers?

BS Maybe - one outside reader for each MS

* Dev. Activities

- Not distributed - next faculty meeting
 - Budgetary implications for projects w external funding
-

* BUDGET

Handout

Ind. Projects

Travel to meetings $\approx$ \$350/yr

Overseas travel same, maybe

* Personel Policy

Research Ass Agts.

BS - ^{Main point} Effect of imp job app for our graduates
See list

Benefited from app, gone in to good academic app clerk

Recent graduate qualified to es. publish material

One ind. app to complete some work
Eg. Jim Armstrong - OIP's on Nippur

No long-term basis
Way of dist. grads.

JJ - Positions not renewable?

BS - App. always 1 year or less

JJ Max?

BS. Modify wording

JJ List on reg. basis - glad got it

Provide on annual basis

Note circ. on new appointments

BS - Un. Policy on Res. Ass.
Have copy

LB #5 } specify
JJ

LB - So few associate rank - Bill Mumane^{eg.}

TB to 77 R.S. did not have to have Ph.D
2 Categories, not comparable in time

BS No Ph.D - exception
J. Sanders MA Architecture

Care by care deviations

Want Set of Routine guidelines

* Priority Statement

Arch. Labs not part of new bldgs.
Vacanted Space in old bldg.

Climate Control exception, no rank order of
priority
eg. Meellen position

Menu of things to be considered

TB

Para. 1

BS We are a research organization
But volunteers dedicated to Mus. or entity

TB Labs duplicate what's on campus
Expensive

BS Opp for multidisciplinary scholars
Already doing in ad hoc way
Space - equipment minor
Staff more imp - Training of students
"This is arch now" - ^{Edge of our} our competitors have
something like this

Want facility concurrence
No other labs on campus in which we could
mobilize the staff

MG - workshops - Computers
eg.

JB - Prehistorical as well
Build bridges outside dept.

MG - Already interested in other depts.

BS - Equip under utilized - already here
eg. SEM, Rem. Sens.
Space, Dedicated Personnel

JJ - In field, or here?

BS Not Proj. Directors
but involved in research design

MS People thinking of
- freelance work for lot of projects
eg. M. Zeder
- MASCA
Not solvable in general way

BS - This is "we will propose"
Approval as priority
Case Statement
↳ proposals we seek to fund
Doc. as 1st step

MG On "that's not bad idea" if lab staff
could all be Res. Associates

BS Faculty head of
group
Res. Ass. man it

JJ - State eqy^o elsewhere on campus

BS This is internal doc.
"topical outline"

JTB See. B & D
Archi. Faculty
Faculty bit
Better related
↳ might
Have to choose between
integrate faculty

JJ - Priorities List
Harvey just does around - Res Associates

BS Part of case statement
want Keep it relatively simple

BS Long Range Priorities

Committee to organize workshops

JTB - Un. willing to support workshops

BS Willing to organize
But not initiate
For one future year - ^{eg.} Spring 1992
Suggestions, Modifications?

BS Doc. violates basic priorities

ER Devote ^{another} meeting to it

BS early in New Year

TB Addressed Arch very well
Other subdisciplines not so well
- Long range terms, new areas

BS False fire alarm
2 Systems
New one went off
Button stuck - Guard ~~set~~ evacuated
building
Faculty member refused to leave
Unexcusable
Bomb threat
"Leave!"
"Don't give guards grief"